

SUN'IY INTELLECT TARIXIDAN

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Annotasiya: Maqolada sun'iy intellekt tarixi, uning dunyo miqyosida rivojlanishi va bu bosqichlardagi ilmiy taraqqiyoti tarixidan qisqacha tahlil keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Intellekt, taraqqiyot, inson, omil, matematik.

Аннотация: В статье дается краткий анализ истории искусственного интеллекта, его развития в мировом масштабе, а также истории научного прогресса на этих этапах.

Ключевые слова: Интеллект, развитие, человек, фактор, математика.

Abstract: The article provides a brief analysis of the history of artificial intelligence, its development on a global scale, as well as the history of scientific progress at these stages.

Keywords: Intelligence, development, man, factor, mathematics.

Sun'iy intellekt sohasida o'tgan asrning o'rtalaridan boshlab tadqiqot ishlari boshlangan. Ingliz matematigi va kriptografi Alan Turing (1912-1954) mazkur yo'nalishda ilk tadqiqot muallifi hisoblanadi. Xususan, 1950 yili texnologiyalar imkoniyatlari insonlarni aql jihatdan ortda qoldirishi haqida savollarga asoslangan maqola chop etilgan. Uning muallifi Alan Turing edi. Keyinchalik olim o'zining nomi bilan atalgan "Turing testi" tartibini ishlab chiqdi. Maqola chop etilganidan so'ng sun'iy intellekt sohasida yangidan-yangi tadqiqotlar amalga oshirildi. Ushbu davr mobaynida olim qarashlarini o'zgartirmagan holda fikrlashda insondan farq qilmaydigan mashinalar haqida ham turli fikrlar bildirib boshlagan.

Sun'iy intellekt sohasida dastlabki ishlar - “Sun'iy intellekt” atamasi 1956 yilga kelib paydo bo'ldi. SHu yilning yozida AQSHning Dartmut universitetida sun'iy tafakkur masalalari bo'yicha anjuman bo'lib o'tdi. Unda Klod SHennon (Bell Laboratories), Nataniel Rochester (IBM), Gerbert Saymon (Karnegi universiteti, Trenchard Mur (Prinston universiteti), Jon Makkarti (Dartmut universiteti), Marvin Minski (Garvard universiteti) kabi olimlar ishtirok etgan.

Ushbu anjumanda ma'ruza qilgan amerikalik informatika sohasidagi olim Jon Makkarti (1927–2011) “Artificial Intelligence” (“Sun'iy tafakkur”) atamasi muallifi sifatida tarixga nom qoldirdi. XX asrning 80-yillari sun'iy intellekt – kashfiyot deya e'tirof etila boshladi. Olimlar ushbu yo'nalishda darsliklar ishlab chiqa boshladilar.

Shuningdek, 1997 yilda shaxmat bo'yicha Jahon chempioni Garri Kasparovni mag'lubiyatga uchratgan mashhur shaxmat dasturi – “Deep Blue” yaratildi. SHu yillarda Yaponiyada neyron tarmoqlari asosida 6-avlod kompyuter loyihasi ishlab chiqilayotgan edi. Shundan so'ng sun'iy intellektga e'tibor kuchaydi. Yirik kompaniyalardan tortib to harbiy muassasalargacha mazkur sohani moliyalashtira boshladi. Natijada yangi texnologiyalar soni oshib, raqobat kuchaydi, sun'iy intellekt vositalari mukammallashib bordi.

Hozirda sun'iy intellektning sohalarga joriy etilishi uchun turli sabablar keltirilmoqda, ulardan uchta eng asosiysini keltirib o'tamiz. Birinchisi, arzon narxlardagi yuqori samarali hisoblash resurslari. Ikkinchisi, ta'lim uchun katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarning mavjudligi. Sun'iy intellekt mahsulining aniq prognozlarni amalga oshirishi uchun u katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlashi kerak. Ushbu omil sabab turli vositalar, xususan, ma'lumotlarni saqlash va qayta ishlashning oddiy hamda arzon vositalari, turli xil algoritmlar yaratildi.

Uchinchisi, sun'iy intellekt mahsulotlari raqobatbardoshlikni mustahkamlaydi. U kompaniyalar xarajatlarini va xavflarni kamaytirishi, bozorga chiqish imkoniyatini kengaytirishi hamda boshqa foydali omillar uchun ko'plab vositalarni

taklif qila oladi. Natijada sun'iy intellekt joriy etilgan kompaniyalar raqobatga anchayin chidamli bo'ladi.

Ammo barcha sohalarda bo'lgani kabi ushbu turdagi innovasiyalarni joriy etishda ham qator qiyinchiliklar mavjud. Xususan, malakali kadrlarning yetishmasligi hamda uni joriy etish uchun ma'lumotlarning kamligi. Sababi ma'lumotlar qanchalik ko'p bo'lsa, sun'iy intellekt bashoratlarning aniqligi shunchalik yuqori bo'ladi.

Sun'iy intellekt infratuzilmani monitoring qilish, katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni to'plash va qayta ishlash, texnik hamda tibbiy diagnostika tizimlari, shaxsiy ta'lim traektoriyalarini yaratish, xulq-atvor tahlillari qilishga imkon beradi. Sun'iy intellekt bu changyutgichlardan kosmik stansiyalarga qadar bo'lgan yechimlarning butun spektridir.

Kompaniya mutaxassislarining fikriga ko'ra, ko'plab korxonalar va tashkilotlar sun'iy intellektning sohaviy muammolarni hal qilishda ko'mak berishini xohlashadi. Ushbu kompaniyalar sun'iy intellekt vositalarini kengaytirib, xavflarni oldindan bilish va barcha jarayonlarni prognozlarga asoslangan holda boshqarishni istaydi. Endilikda tadqiqotchilar oldida yanada murakkab vazifalar turibdi. Xususan, internet taraqqiyoti, texnologik muammolarni bartaraf etish, raqamli iqtisodiyot uchun yangi vositalar yaratish lozim. Shuningdek, o'zbekistonlik tadqiqotchilarning eng asosiy vazifalaridan biri esa sun'iy intellektning ilm-fanga joriy etilishida yaqindan ko'mak berishidir.

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